

Impact and management of pest species due to climate change in Sikkim's agro-ecosystem

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Abstract

A semi-systematic literature review was conducted to understand the growing impact of climate change on insect pest dynamics within the Sikkim Himalaya agro-ecosystem, the world's first fully organic state (Bhutia, 2024; Gopi et al., 2016). This biodiversity hotspot's delicate balance is impacted by climate variability, such as rising temperatures and erratic rainfall, which increases pest and disease migration and severely threatens food security and rural livelihoods (Sharma et al., 2009; Pradhan & Devy, 2018). The research focuses on four key crops: the high-value cash crops, large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum*) and mandarin orange (*Citrus reticulata*), and the staple food crops, maize (*Zea mays*) and rice (*Oryza sativa*). The analysis reveals that minor pests are transitioning into major pests and affecting the economy, most notably the invasive Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) in maize (Chamling et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2023). Furthermore, large cardamom production is facing significant declines due to viral diseases like Chirkey and Foorkey (Meher & Debnath, 2025a; Sharma et al., 2016), and the citrus industry is threatened by pests such as the Citrus Long Horned Beetle (*Anoplophora versteegi*) (Pradhan & Devy, 2018). The resilience framework is largely dependent on combining scientific bio-rational controls with extensive Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITKs), which use indigenous plants and cultural practices for pest management, in light of the state's organic mandate (Raj et al., 2021; Gopi et al., 2016). To protect Sikkim's distinctive sustainable agricultural model, this research emphasizes the urgent need for a coordinated approach integrating ecological health, climate adaptation, and supportive policy (Sharma et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2022).

Introduction

Agricultural ecosystems worldwide face constant challenges from insect pests, leading to significant crop losses. To prevent this, there is a heavy reliance on chemical pesticides (Chaplin Kramer et al., 2011). There are numerous risks to the economy, environment, and public health posed by this reliance on synthetic inputs; more sustainable approaches to pest management must be looked into for the management of pests. (Da Silva et al., 2022).

In the eastern Himalayas, Sikkim is located at latitudes of 27°5' N to 20°9' N and longitudes of 87° 59' E to 88°56' E. Positioned in north-east, Sikkim is the second smallest state of India between Nepal in the west and Bhutan in the east, China in the north and West Bengal in the south, covering an area of 7,096 km. The Eastern Himalayas, particularly the region of Sikkim, stand out as a globally significant hotspot for both biodiversity and agrobiodiversity, characterised by its unique agro-ecological zones. This diversity is reflected through its five distinct climatic zones, six forest types, three soil orders, 26 soil subgroups, 21 glaciers, 28 mountain ranges and peaks, 227 lakes and wetlands, and over 104 rivers and streams. Despite covering only 7,096 sq. km, which amounts to just 0.22% of India's total geographical area. The state's landscape includes low, mid, and high hills, alpine areas, and snow-covered regions. Out of the total area, about 1.09 lakh hectares is arable land, representing around 16% of the state's geography (*Biodiversity-Seminar-Sujata-Upadhyay*).

Sikkim has emerged as a global exemplar in sustainable agriculture by becoming the first fully organic state worldwide, officially achieving 100% organic certification in 2016. This transition contains approximately 75,000 hectares of agricultural land and benefited over 66,000 farming families (Bhutia, 2024). Sikkim is an incredible reminder of the vulnerability and abundance of nature, with its extraordinary landscapes supporting both vibrant human cultures and amazing biodiversity. More than two-thirds of the state's population is dependent on farming for its sustenance indirectly or directly which is central to the state's rural identity (Pradhan & Devy, 2018). In addition to producing food, Sikkim's terraces and fields serve as living examples of resilience, adaptation, and traditional knowledge. However, despite being India's first fully organic state, this unique region is under increasing pressure from environmental change, climate variability, and the ongoing difficulty of controlling agricultural pests (Gopi et al., 2016).

Unpredictability is added to this delicate balance by climate change: unpredictable rains, rising average temperatures, and extreme weather events increased influence of insect pest and disease migration and dynamics, disrupting crop yields and food security (Sharma et al., 2009). In orange orchards, farmers now have to deal with invasive species and new outbreaks brought on by changing ecological regimes (Pradhan & Devy, 2018).

The purpose of this research is to see how climate change is affecting Sikkim's four main crops: two high-value cash crops, large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum*) and mandarin orange (*Citrus reticulata*), and two staple food crops, maize (*Zea mays*) and rice (*Oryza sativa*). These crops, each with unique ecological needs, economic significance, and risk qualities in the face of emerging climatic variability, are essential to the food security, livelihoods, and cultural identity of Sikkim's agricultural communities.

Food Crops: Rice and Maize

The main food crops grown by marginal farmers in Sikkim's various agroclimatic zones are maize and rice. Rice is particularly vulnerable to changes in rainfall patterns and temperature swings because it is frequently grown in terraced paddies under monsoon-dependent rainfed conditions. According to studies, rice is the crop most vulnerable to climate variability in the area. Variable precipitation, extended dry spells, and variations in temperature disrupt planting schedules, increase the incidence of pests and diseases, and reduce yields (Sharma & Rai, 2025).

The second staple, maize, which is typically grown in mid-hill regions, is essential to traditional diets and subsistence farming systems. Similar issues with water availability and rising pest pressures affect it, particularly the spread of invasive species like the fall armyworm, which is made easier by rising temperatures (Tamang et al., 2023). Given their limited availability to irrigation and adaptation technologies, farmers of both rice and maize report that these weather-related stresses worsen socioeconomic vulnerabilities.

Cash Crops: Large Cardamom and Mandarin Orange

The high-value spice crop known as "green gold," or large cardamom, is deeply rooted in Sikkim's agroforestry landscapes and economy. Its cultivation in the subtropical to temperate zones is dependent upon extremely specific climatic and altitudinal conditions. Over the past 20 years, the crop has experienced significant productivity declines as a result of changing temperature and precipitation patterns, an increase in fungal diseases linked to humidity, pests, and pollinator population disruption (Chakraborty et al., 2019; Pradhan et al., 2025). Changes toward alternative cropping systems or income diversification are caused by the significant impact of this decline on farmer incomes and rural livelihoods.

A major crop in agriculture for a long time, mandarin oranges are widely grown between 600 and 1500 meters above sea level. Following the decline of large cardamom, it has recently shown an increase in popularity as a substitute cash crop. However, the citrus industry is dealing with insect pests like mealybugs and the citrus long horned beetle, as well as new diseases like citrus dieback, powdery mildew, and viral infections (Pradhan & Devy, 2018). These pest and disease issues are made worse by climatic changes that raise temperature variability and humidity, which calls for creative organic management techniques that comply with Sikkim's organic certification demands.

Objective

To identify key crop-pest interactions and their ecological roles through a systematic literature review.

Methodology

A Systematic Literature Review will be conducted targeting peer-reviewed scientific articles and white papers using various standards libraries, including Google Scholar, Web of

Science, Scopus, Science Direct and ResearchGate. The search string that will be used is: ("crop damage" OR "pest suppression" OR "biological control") AND ("agroecosystem" OR "farming system" OR "agriculture") AND ("functional diversity" OR "species richness" OR "trophic interaction") OR "maze and pests" OR "rice and pests and himalayan region" OR ("mandarian orange or pests") OR ("cardamom and pests and climate change") AND ("climate change or agricultural pests)

Inclusion Criteria

Category	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Geographic Location	Research conducted in Sikkim or relevant to Sikkim's agriculture	Studies from locations outside Sikkim without direct relevance
Crop Focus	Research conducted in Sikkim or relevant to Sikkim's agriculture, focusing on four major crops	Studies from locations outside Sikkim without direct relevance
Pest Management Methods	Eco-friendly, organic, or traditional pest management techniques	Chemical pesticide-based approaches only
Time Frame	Published within the last 20 years	Studies published before the selected time frame
Publication Type	Peer-reviewed articles, theses, conference proceedings, grey literature	Editorials, letters, news articles

Prisma flow chart

Adapted from: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

Results

Overview of Included Studies

This meta-analysis synthesises findings from several studies and papers focusing on pest and disease management for four major key crops in specific agricultural ecosystems of Sikkim. The crops that were analysed include **large cardamom (Amomum subulatum)**, **maize (Zea mays)**, **mandarin orange (Citrus reticulata)**, and **rice (Oryza sativa)**. The aim was to identify major pests, their associated diseases, and traditional, as well as modern pest management practices.

Crop	Scientific Name	Major Pests and Viral Diseases	Bio-rational/Ecological Control Methods
Large Cardamom	Amomum subulatum	Insect Pests: Shoot Fly (<i>Merchlorops dimorphus</i>), Leaf Caterpillars (<i>Artona chorista</i>), Stem Borer (<i>Glyphipterix sp.</i>), Aphids (<i>Mollitrichosiphum sp.</i> - vector). Viral Diseases: Chirkey (LCCV), Foorkey (CBDV)	Cultural Control: Immediate roguing (removal and destruction) of infected plants (for viruses). Bio-rational Control: Evaluation and application of botanicals, bio-pesticides , for insect pests (especially shoot fly and vectors).
Maize	Zea mays	Soil dwellers, foliage feeders, Stem Borers, Flower/Cob feeders (general <i>kharif</i> crop pests in the region).	Integrated Pest Management (IPM): Focus on preventive cultural practices (e.g., proper sanitation, intercropping). Bio-control: Utilization of natural enemies (predators/parasitoids) and bio-rational products.
Mandarin Orange	Citrus reticulata	Various altitude-dependent insect pests (e.g., leaf miners, fruit flies, psyllids common to Himalayan horticulture).	Traditional Practices: Utilising time-tested indigenous methods. Ecosystem Management: Conserving pollinators (<i>Apis cerana</i> , Bumblebees) to ensure fruit set and quality.
Rice	Oryza sativa	Stem Borers, Leaf Folders, Plant Hoppers (general cereal pests in the region).	Cultural Practices: Water management, timing of planting, and traditional methods.

Pest Complexes Specific to Crops

1- *Amomum subulatum* Roxb., or large cardamom

Both insect pests and viral diseases pose serious threats to large cardamom, a plant in the Zingiberaceae family. Aphids (*Mollitrichosiphum* sp.), leaf caterpillars (*Artona chorista*), stem borer (*Glyphipterix* sp.), shoot fly (*Merochlorops dimorphus*), and white grubs (*Holotrichia* spp.) are the main insect pests. Among the major pests, shoot flies were found to be the most common (44%) and were followed by leaf caterpillars and stem borers (Avasthe & Bhutia, 2018.; Raj et al., 2021a).

Viral Diseases: Two terrible viral diseases, Chirkey and Foorkey, have a significant impact on large cardamom. Chirkey disease, caused by the Large Cardamom Chirkey Virus (LCCV), results in yield losses ranging from 33.97% to 52.84% and is characterised by mosaic symptoms with pale streaks on leaves. With yield losses ranging from 36.30% to 55.47%, foot-and-mouth disease, which is caused by the Cardamom Bushy Dwarf Virus (CBDV), results in bushy dwarf clumps and excessive sprouting. (Meher & Debnath, 2025a; Sharma et al., 2016).

Traditional Management: Farmers use nine different traditional methods, such as gathering and burning infested plant parts, applying leaf extracts from tobacco, Titepati, Chillowney, and Indreni to chew and sucking pests, and covering cardamom clumps with dried leaves to protect them from mammalian pests (Raj et al., 2021) .

2 - *Zea mays* L., or maize

Cut worm (*Agrotis ipsilon*), stem borer (*Scirpophaga incertulas*), army worm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), semi-looper (*Achaea janata*), and cob borer (*Helicoverpa armigera*) are among the insect pests that pose a threat to maize cultivation. In recent years, the fall army worm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) has become a serious hazard.(Lal et al., 2017).

Disease Control: The main diseases are bacterial stalk rot (*Erwinia* spp.), Maydis leaf blight (*Bipolaris maydis*), and Turcicum leaf blight (*Helminthosporium turcicum*).

Management Strategies: Pre-sowing seed treatment with bio-fertilisers, hand-picking adult moths, crop rotation, adjusting the timing of sowing and harvesting, and applying neem formulations are examples of integrated approaches. (Dhillon et al., 2014).

3 - *Citrus reticulata*, or Mandarin orange

Thirteen distinct pest species from four taxonomic orders—Coleoptera, Diptera, Hemiptera, and Lepidoptera—are encountered in citrus cultivation. Citrus psylla (*Diaphorina citri*), red scale (*Aonidiella aurantii*), Japanese beetle (*Popilia japonica*), citrus long-horned beetle (*Anoplophora versteegi*), and fruit fly (*Bactrocera dorsalis*) are among the major pests .(Pradhan & Devy, 2019a).

New Pest Concerns: While some pests, such as red scale, are relatively new to farmers or have increased in recent years, Japanese beetle abundance and attack intensity increase during the spring and monsoon seasons .(Ghimire et al., 2024).

Traditional Management: To combat pests and diseases, farmers use kerosene, cow dung, cow urine, and local plants like *Artemisia vulgaris* and *Eupatorium* mixed with cow urine as sprays.

4 - *Oryza sativa* L., or rice

A complex of 23 insect pest species from 7 orders and 14 families coexist in rice ecosystems. Stem borer (*Scirpophaga incertulas*), leaf folder (*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*), gundhi bug (*Leptocorisa orientalis*), and rice thrips (*Baliothrips biformis*) are among the major pests.

Disease Complex: Sheath rot, sheath blight, stem rot, false smut, bacterial leaf blight, blast, brown spot, and tungro virus are important diseases.

Management Strategies: Farmers use light traps, preventative neem oil applications, field sanitation, and the positioning of repellent plant branches (*Artemisia vulgaris*, *Schima wallichii*, and *Chromoleana odoratum*).

Traditional Knowledge Systems

Physical/mechanical, plant-based, animal-based, cultural, and biological approaches are the five main categories of pest management practices that are covered in the analysis of Sikkim farmers' extensive traditional ecological knowledge. (ICAR Research Complex for NEH Region, Sikkim Centre, Tadong, Gangtok, Sikkim (737 102), India et al., 2016)

Native Plant Resources: Titepati (*Artemisia vulgaris*), Chillowney, Indreni, tobacco, neem, *Eupatorium* and mint are among the many plant species that farmers use to control pests. These methods show a deep comprehension of secondary metabolites found in plants and their ability to kill pests (ibid.).

Cultural practices: Using techniques like mixed/multiple cropping, zero tillage, clean cultivation, slash and burn, green manuring, sequential cropping and harvesting, and fallowing, traditional farming systems integrate built-in pest management mechanisms.

Pollination and Ecological Interactions

Biology of Pollination

Bumble bees (*Bombus breviceps* and *B. haemorrhoidalis*) are the main pollinators of large cardamom, which has specific pollination needs. Altitude and the availability of bee species affect pollination efficiency, which has a major effect on yield results. (Kishore et al., 2011).

Pollination services for Mandarin oranges are dominated by the common honey bee (*Apis cerana*), which is followed by stingless bees, seed bugs, beetles, and a variety of hoverfly species. These pollinators increase crop productivity by feeding on pollen and nectar. (Pradhan & Devy, 2019b).

Climate Change and Pest Dynamics

The dynamics of pests in the area have been greatly impacted by climate change. Because of periodic climatic variations and shifts in natural enemy populations, minor pests have become major threats. For example, in growing regions, *Holotrichia* spp., which were once a major pest of ginger, are now a major pest of cardamom plantations. (Avasthe & Bhutia, 2018.; Meher & Debnath, 2025b).

Implications for the Economy and Sustainability

The agricultural economy of Sikkim is seriously threatened by the known pest complexes. Viral diseases alone pose a serious threat to the large cardamom production, which is valued at about 3,863 MT annually from 26,459 hectares. In a similar vein, the cultivation of mandarin oranges, which spans 12,380 hectares and sustains more than 12,000 farming families, suffers large losses due to new pest problems (Avasthe & Bhutia, 2018.).

Discussion

As the first fully organic state in the world and a globally significant hotspot in agrobiodiversity, the Sikkim Himalayas offer a unique case study in climate resilience and sustainable mountain agriculture (Singh et al., 2022). However, newly developed and returning pest and disease complexes are now posing a serious and growing threat to this delicate mountain ecosystem, which is marked by its vulnerability to climate change (Meher & Debnath, 2025; Sharma et al., 2009). Given its low adaptation capacity, this region is particularly vulnerable to these changes, particularly for the poor and marginalized who depend heavily on natural resources for their subsistence (Sharma et al., 2009).

I. The Acceleration of Natural Stress by Climate Change

According to Sharma et al. (2016), climate change is a powerful ecological threat that is drastically altering the status and geographic distribution of agricultural pests and diseases throughout the Himalayan region. In high-value cash crops like large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum*), changes in temperature, precipitation patterns, and humidity are directly associated with a higher risk of specific climate-induced diseases (Singh et al., 2015, Meher & Debnath, 2025). Because of this environmental instability, established pest management hierarchies need to be reviewed because organisms that were once thought of as minor or occasional are now claiming to be the main economic constraints and causing distress to the farmers (Meher & Debnath, 2025). Developing truly climate-resilient cropping systems that endure these shock events while preserving the integrity of the organic status becomes the main goal in this difficult situation (Singh et al., 2022).

II. The Change in Major Pest Status in Important Crops

The increased strain on Sikkim's three main crops – large cardamom, maize, and mandarin orange – is the most obvious example of this shifting ecology. Stem borer which was a pest for ginger has now shifted to cardamom.

Large Cardamom: The Crisis of Cash Crops

Numerous insect and mammalian pests, as well as serious viral and fungal diseases, seriously limit large cardamom, a crucial cash crop in the area (Vijayan, 2015; Deka et al., 2016; Sharma et al., 2016). Although a larger complex of pests, such as the Stem Borer (*Chilades pandava*), Rhizome Rot (fungal/bacterial complex), and Chirkey/Foorkey viral diseases, collectively reduce the yield potential, the Shoot Borer (*Dichocrocis punctiferalis*) continues to be the most economically devastating pest (Deka et al., 2016; Raj et al., 2021). Both the effects of climate change and agro-economic changes are directly responsible for the decline in large cardamom production systems, requiring a revival strategy (Sharma et al., 2016). Research demonstrates that in order to sustain productivity, the prevalence of pests in this organic agro-ecosystem calls for efficient management using bio-rationals and integrated strategies (Raj et al., 2021).

The Invasion of Fall Armyworm and Maize

The recent introduction of the invasive Fall Armyworm (FAW) (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) has brought attention to maize (*Zea mays*), a vital food staple (Chamling et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2023). A new and quickly growing threat, this highly polyphagous pest has quickly established itself in the Eastern Himalayan region (Singh et al., 2023). Field inspections after farmers in Sikkim initially reported FAW infestation in maize fields in April 2020 confirmed the extent of the potential damage, particularly in the crop's early growth stages (Chamling et al., 2020). The growing threat of other maize pests associated with the effects of climate change further highlights maize's vulnerability (Meher & Debnath, 2025).

Pests of Mandarin Oranges

As the most destructive pest in the area, the dangerous Citrus Long Horned Beetle (*Anoplophora versteegi*) is the main threat to the Mandarin Orange (*Citrus reticulata*), another important horticultural crop (Pradhan & Devy, 2018). A complex of secondary but widespread pests follows, which include the stem borer, the Japanese beetle (*Popillia japonica*), and four dominant Hemipterans (collectively known as laikira) (Pradhan & Devy, 2018). To provide a baseline for future research and focused efforts to manage by government agencies, it is necessary to document these pest profiles.

Rice Crop's vulnerability

Despite the valley's agricultural paddy systems' longstanding resilience, these problems still affect rice (*Oryza sativa*), an essential component of regional food security (Chhetry & Belbahri, 2009). Insect pests continue to pose a threat, necessitating thorough research into organic, regional remedies. In order to keep the breeding pipeline focused on resilient local germplasm rather than chemical dependence, studies in the area concentrate on finding local rice genotypes that show inherent resistance to important sucking pests like the Brown Planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens*) (Bodhnapod, 2018). Additionally, the stability of rice production under current organic systems depends significantly on constant surveillance and the application of traditional ecological knowledge (Chhetry & Belbahri, 2009).

III. The Framework for Organic Resilience: Combining ITKs and Bio-Rationals

The careful coexistence of scientifically proven biological agents and Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITKs) have allowed Sikkim to successfully transition to the world's first fully organic state, resulting in an advanced system of decentralized organic resilience (Gopi et al., 2016). This integrated model is critical because, while the organic mandate is vital for ecosystem health, organic methods have sometimes proven less immediately effective in combating sudden, severe outbreaks compared to conventional chemicals, presenting a challenge to land productivity (Das & Bhattacharyya, 2018; Mishra et al., 2021). The ITKs (Indigenous Technical Knowledge) represent generations of accumulated wisdom used by farmers to manage pests and diseases without relying on external inputs (Gopi et al., 2016). These practices highlight a deep ecological understanding of pest life cycles and natural plant defences.

Recent Integration of Bio-Rational

The organic requirement calls for modern, bio-rational controls when conventional approaches need to be strengthened. This covers the use of botanical formulations and microbial agents. For example, recent studies have confirmed the usefulness of bio-rationals in the organic agro-ecosystem in managing important large cardamom pests (Raj et al., 2021). Likewise, the unexpected emergence of the invasive Fall Armyworm (FAW) (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) in maize required an immediate integrated pest management (IPM) approach that included neem-based formulations and the use of the entomopathogenic fungus (*Metarrhizium anisopliae*). This demonstrated the vital collaboration between scientific bio-agents and on-farm organic action (Chamling et al., 2020).

Conclusion

The agro-ecosystem of the Sikkim Himalaya is extremely vulnerable to the negative effects of climate change, a global phenomenon that disproportionately affects vulnerable mountain regions, as this analysis highlights (Sharma et al., 2009; Meher & Debnath, 2025; Sharma, Arya, & Bachheti, 2024). Despite being a landmark achievement, the shift to a fully organic state has come across significant obstacles, especially due to the growing incidence

of newly emerging pests such as the Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) in maize (Singh et al., 2023; Chamling et al., 2020) and ongoing pest and disease threats to cash crops like ginger and large cardamom (Deka et al., 2016; Raj et al., 2021).

There is an urgent need for strong, evidence-based growth strategies because of the documented decline in large cardamom production systems brought on by diseases, pests, and climate change (Sharma et al., 2016). Farmers are utilizing traditional and indigenous knowledge (Upadhyay & Rai, 2022; Gopi et al., 2016; Chhetry & Belbahri, 2009; Mishra et al., 2021), as well as strategies such as modifying planting dates, managing nutrients, and providing supplemental irrigation (Deb & Babel, 2015). Therefore, the resilience of the Sikkim agricultural model is based on a combination of the region's rich agrobiodiversity (Rahman & Karuppaiyan, 2011), traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) (Gudade et al., 2013; Lepcha et al., 2025), and scientific findings that predict a significant reduction in maize yield under future climate scenarios (Deb & Babel, 2015). In the end, preserving Sikkim's natural integrity and farmer livelihoods requires a comprehensive and inclusive strategy that acknowledges the close relationship between climate adaptation, traditional knowledge, and ecological health

Future Directions

Advocate for Policy Support and Incentives

1. The clear promotion of policy encouragement and incentives needs to be translated into practical systems that make the sustainable choice for the farmer's most secure and profitable one.

Building Capacity and Sharing Knowledge

2. In the face of new pest arrivals, this foundation serves as the operational key for creating innovative, expedient control solutions. Farmers require quick, localized knowledge when a new pest appears, such as the Fall Armyworm on maize or the Brown Planthopper on rice in new areas.

The agricultural system can achieve actual, organic resilience and sustainability by combining these strategies, where smart policy makes eco-friendly decisions more affordable and increased capacity allows farmers to quickly develop and implement effective strategies against climate-driven threats.

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